

FILIPINO J1 TEACHERS' ADAPTATION TO AMERICAN EARLY CHILDHOOD CLASSROOM CONTEXT: A CASE OF MARICOPA COUNTY'S EARLY CHILDHOOD

Jossie Pine L. Moore
Maria Alona A. Galendez, EdD-ECE

Lourdes College, Inc. Cagayan de Oro, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18289006>

ABSTRACT

Globalization has increasingly expanded opportunities for international teacher exchange, yet the lived experiences of Filipino J-1 Early Childhood Education (ECE) teachers adapting to American classrooms remain underexplored. This study aims to investigate how Filipino J-1 teachers navigate cultural, linguistic, and pedagogical transitions while integrating Filipino values into their professional practice in Maricopa County, Arizona. Employing a qualitative phenomenological approach, in-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted with five J-1 teachers to capture detailed narratives of their motivations, challenges, adaptation strategies, professional growth, and cultural contributions. Participants scheduled interviews according to their availability, with sessions lasting 30 to 60 minutes and carefully transcribed for rigorous analysis. The findings revealed five overarching themes: teachers' pursuit of personal and professional advancement, management of inclusive and adaptive teaching for diverse learners, strengthening collaboration and culturally-informed professionalism, transformation of pedagogical practices through global exposure, and integration of Filipino culture within value-driven instruction. Teachers were motivated by economic upliftment, career enrichment, and international exposure, yet faced challenges in linguistic comprehension, accommodating diverse learners, and adjusting to student-centered pedagogical approaches. Adaptation strategies included relationship-building, intercultural collaboration, and professional reflection, which enhanced both teaching effectiveness and workplace cohesion. Furthermore, teachers perceived themselves as cultural ambassadors, fostering inclusivity, global awareness, and intercultural understanding among students and colleagues. Overall, the study highlights the multidimensional impact

of J-1 teachers, emphasizing their role in bridging cultures and advancing professional competencies. Future research may explore longitudinal outcomes of J-1 experiences and comparative studies across states, educational levels, or cultural contexts to inform international teacher exchange programs.

Keywords: *Filipino J-1 teachers, Early childhood education, Cultural adaptation, J1 Visa Program, American Classroom*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, significant changes were seen in the world; all thanks to globalization. Today, a number of international policies and programs have been enacted to govern and oversee exchange workers all across the world. The roots of globalization are far-reaching; it has extended its branches into the educational context. Universities all around the globe have become increasingly welcoming to foreign-exchanged educators and students (Uytico, 2020).

One international program that Filipino teachers have embraced is the Teacher Exchange Program offered by the US Department of State. Under J1 Visa of the program, teachers are given the opportunity to teach in the United States of America (USA) provided that they meet all the eligibility requirements. The Teacher Exchange Program was first initiated in 1987, which is open to 50 selected countries like New Zealand, Canada, Australia, Mexico, Spain, Chile, and the Philippines (Oris & Caballes, 2024).

As cited by Lockhart (2021), the central objectives of international exchange programs are to allow individuals see new and fresh perspectives, discover novel ideas and learnings, and experience different cultures and practices. The J1 visa program allows Filipino teachers to experience all these things and incorporate them to their teaching approach.

A huge number of Filipino teachers have already been teaching in the United States of America. According to Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2023), more than 1500 Filipino teachers have already left the Philippines to teach in USA. Filipino instructors are exploring this potential through J1 visa (Uytico, 2020). Citing the data from Oris and Caballes (2024), there is a huge leap in the numbers of Filipino J-1 Visa teachers teaching in the US. From 1521 Filipino j-1 Teachers, it rose up to 2166 in the year 2021. This made the Philippines as the number one provider of J-1 Visa teachers in the USA.

Many Filipino teachers desire to further develop their teaching careers abroad by assimilating to different educational practices. Aside from this, the opportunity to be able to travel and live into a foreign country with an entirely different culture, and to be able to grow personally and professionally as an educator are some of the extra factors. However, notwithstanding the growing number of literatures anchored on Filipino educators teaching abroad, there remains a dearth in the literature highlighting actual experiences of J1 Filipino teachers in adapting into the entirely new environment of educational field and their specific adaptation process strategies.

International divides are increasingly closing, which make it even more hard for international educators to adapt to their new environment (Berger, 2021). Owing to this, this study undermined the cross-cultural experiences and the unique methods of Filipino J1 teachers in Maricopa County District in adapting to their new educational environment. Through this research, aspiring J1 Filipino teachers will have a clear picture of the cultural and educational experiences of other J1 teachers, which will help them prepare and equip themselves for this endeavor.

Research Questions

In light of this study, the following research questions will be pursued:

1. Why do J1 Filipino ECE teachers participate in the J1 teacher exchange program?
2. What challenges do J1 Filipino ECE teachers face in terms of making adjustments to American educational systems and classroom environments?
3. How do J1 Filipino teachers adapt to cultural differences in the workplace and the community?
4. What professional growth or development have the J1 Filipino ECE teachers experienced as a product of the program?
5. How do the J1 Filipino ECE teachers perceive the impact of their presence on their students and colleagues in terms of cultural exchange?

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the study was to get to know the cross-cultural experiences and coping mechanisms of five Filipino J1 teachers in the Maricopa County District, Arizona. The phenomenological approach was adopted to streamline on the actual experiences of the teachers in adapting to a new culture and a new teacher environment. The research accorded them the significance of the voices of the people involved and carried out the ethical process in a manner that was both honest and fair. In this way, the study could demonstrate the real-life experiences of Filipino J1 teachers and contribute valuable information to the research on international teacher exchange programs.

The study was done in Maricopa County, Arizona which is characterized by high population, cultural diversity and good educational system. The reason why this location was selected is that it offered a good environment to understand the experiences of Filipino teachers working overseas. The schools in the district that employed Filipino J1 teachers were used to select the participants. The district superintendent was requested to give permission first and the Institutional Review Board (IRB) gave approval. The participants were invited to take part in the interviews by giving a short demographic survey to ensure that they fit the criteria.

Data were collected through semi structured interviews since the teachers were free to speak out their experiences yet a guide of questions was used. The interview schedules were set according to the availability of the participants to accommodate their

work schedules. Informed consent was provided a week prior to the interviews and the participants were well informed of the aim of the study, the fact that their information would remain confidential and their right to withdraw at any point was clarified. The interviews were done online taking between 30 and 60 minutes. The interviews were recorded with permission, and some of the answers were written down. All the records were stored in a safe location and accessed by the researcher and authorized analysts. The interviews were transcribed immediately in order to ensure that the information was up to date.

There were ethical considerations that were strictly adhered to in this study. The Belmont Report principles were used in the research. The participants were respected by ensuring that they were involved in the study on a voluntary and informed basis. The aspect of beneficence was applied by ensuring that no harm was done to the participants and maintaining their confidentiality. Justice was observed through the process of choosing the participants and ensuring that the outcomes of the study can be utilized in enhancing the exchange of teachers internationally.

RESULTS

This study explored the experiences of five Filipino J-1 Early Childhood Education (The ECE teachers in the United States. It dwelled into the reasons why they were in the program, their issues, the adaptation process, skills that they acquired and how they transmitted their culture in schools.

In the case of Research Question 1 (RQ1), the study established that the teachers enrolled in the J-1 program due to personal as well as professional reasons. Most of them desired to get higher wages, better work life, and an opportunity to take care of their families. Some just wanted to expand their career in another country and have a teaching experience. All these reasons demonstrate that the teachers were driven by both the money and personal ambitions.

In Research Question 2 (RQ2), the teachers had difficulties accommodating to a new culture and language. They could not comprehend the American accent and even expressions. They had to also adapt to teaching language-differentiated students. The process of managing students with special needs and adhering to the U.S. teaching practices, including classroom behavior rules, the use of technology, and the student-centered teaching were also difficult. These issues demonstrated how difficult it was to adapt to new school regime.

For Research Question 3 (RQ3), the teachers accommodated with students, co-teachers, and parents by establishing good relationships. They collaborated with others closely, and applied Filipino values, respect, patience, and care. They integrated these values together with American pedagogies, which produced a conducive and accommodating classroom atmosphere.

In the case of Research Question 4 (RQ4) the teachers responded that they had

grown professionally in the process of working abroad. They improved in handling the classrooms, clarification of lessons, and application of various teaching methods. They also got to know how to use technology in a better way and enhanced their communication skills. These assisted them in educating pupils of other origins in a more productive manner.

In Research Question 5 (RQ5), the teachers were cultural ambassadors at their schools. They taught the students and colleagues Filipino culture, values and traditions. This assisted students in appreciating cultural differences and valuing differences, and allowed them to have a more inclusive learning environment.

The study, in general, indicates that the experiences of Filipino J-1 ECE teachers were associated with numerous challenges and learning opportunities. The program not only enabled them to become better teachers and persons but also enabled them to play a positive role at schools in the United States with their abilities and cultural ethics.

DISCUSSION

RQ 1: Why do J1 Filipino ECE teachers participate in the J1 teacher exchange program?

THEME	CATEGORIES
1. Pursuing Personal and Professional Advancement	Category 1: Economic and Personal Upliftment Category 2: Career Enrichment and Global Experience

The results showed that J-1 Filipino ECE teachers were motivated primarily by personal and professional reasons which are consistent with the Push-Pull Theory of Migration, where low wages back home drive the teachers to the country abroad and good compensation abroad draws them to the US (Peralta et al., 2024; Shi et al., 2024). These responses are also in agreement with Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory, where it makes a distinction between the financial considerations and intrinsic causes like recognition and development (Nickerson, 2025). Aside from compensation, non-monetary responses such as more intimate classes, cutting-edge technologies, and better facilities, were also critical, in your own offer to job satisfaction boosters emphasized by Osei and Zhuang (2020) and supportive of documentation of facilitating environments for retaining educators (Syuzairi et al., 2023; Arnold and Rahimi in 2025). Moreover, the teachers were interested in professional development and global experience, which was consistent with the Experiential Learning Theory (Saracho, 2023). Their decisions were also reflective of Filipino cultural values such as the pakikipagkapwa - to reconcile career development with family responsibilities utang na loob (Cahilog et al., 2023; Soriano et al., 2024).

RQ2: What challenges do J1 Filipino ECE teachers face in terms of making adjustments to American educational systems and classroom environments?

Theme	Categories
2. Managing Inclusive and Adaptive Teaching for Diverse Learners	Category 1: Cultural and Linguistic Transition Category 2: Attending to students with Special Needs Category 3: Pedagogical and Instructional Adjustment

Results show that Filipino J-1 Early Childhood Education (ECE) teachers encounter challenges in adjusting to U.S. classrooms, mainly under Cultural and Linguistic Transition and Pedagogical and Instructional Adjustment. Teachers were linguistically challenged by American accents, colloquial terms, and interactions with multilingual students, particularly Spanish speakers, which frequently deterred them from engaging in professional development (AlShihry, 2023; Hesson et al., 2024). Culturally, they mediated with heterogeneous expectations and accommodating special needs pupils, evidencing training gaps (Mabanag et al., 2024; Gal et al., 2025). These challenges are consistent with Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory and Berry's Acculturation Framework since teachers mediated between collectivist Filipino mores and individualistic U.S. values (Piotrowska & Piotrowska, 2023; van der Zee & van Oudenhoven, 2022). Pedagogically, difficulties involved handling differences in behavior (Chakma, 2025; Culha & Yilmaz, 2023), implementing technology (Kalyani, 2024; Bhat, 2023), and adjusting to student-centered teaching (Wang et al., 2025). Overall, results highlight that institutional support, intercultural competence, and professional training are required to increase teacher effectiveness.

RQ 3: How do J1 Filipino teachers adapt to cultural differences in the workplace and the community?

Theme	Categories
3. Strengthening Professional Collaboration through Technology and Enhanced Communication	Category 1: Sustaining Collaboration and Relationships Category 2: Culturally-Informed Professionalism Category 3: Improved Communication and Interpersonal Skills

The findings for Research Question 3 (RQ3) show that Filipino J-1 teachers dealt with cultural differences in the U.S. schools and communities through one main idea: adaptive resiliency through collaboration and cultural responsiveness. The teachers believed the importance of building good relationships. They earned the trust of the students by understanding their background and empathy. They also maintained good relationships with parents and fellow teachers through school activity participation and

close working with others (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; Afzal, 2023). These practices support studies which say strong relationships help to improve motivation, sense of belonging and professional growth of international teachers (Romijn, 2021; Gu et al., 2021).

Another important finding was that the teachers demonstrated culturally informed professionalism. This helped them to adapt to the culture in the US school while still keeping their Filipino values. Because they were sensitive to cultural differences and learned behaviors that are acceptable, they gained respect from their colleagues. This reflects the ideas of culturally responsive teaching in which teachers respect and value different cultures (Gay, 2018; Sleeter, 2017). Their professionalism, guided by Filipino values such as respect, patience and empathy have helped them to manage the classrooms well and practice ethical teaching (Eden et al., 2024; Darling-Hammond and Hyler, 2020).

In general, the Filipino J-1 teachers managed to overcome cultural differences through teamwork and professionalism based on good values. These practices supported the creation of inclusive and supportive school environments, and made them better teachers.

RQ 4: What professional growth or development have the J1 Filipino ECE teachers experienced as a product of the program?

Theme	Categories
4. Transforming Differences through Meaningful Pedagogical Practices and Improved Interpersonal Skills	Category 1: Improved Pedagogical Knowledge Category 2: Use of Technical Learning Resources

The outcomes of RQ4 identify professional development of J-1 Filipino ECE teachers in the United States under the one primary theme: Transformation of Pedagogical Practices through Global Exposure. Teachers built stronger pedagogical capacities by using differentiated instruction to support varied learning requirements and explicit instruction to make the subject matter clear and scaffold learners (Dhakal, 2024; Klingner & Boardman, 2019). Teachers also built classroom management using techniques like cooperative learning and the gradual release model, building inclusivity and student engagement (Abidin, 2024; Putra & Yanto, 2025).

Similarly, educators enhanced technology incorporation, employing resources such as smartboards and applications to develop vibrant, learner-focused pedagogy, in keeping with the TPACK model (Adipat et al., 2023; Kalyani, 2024). Student-engaging methods improved learner participation (Hasanov et al., 2021; Sankalaite et al., 2023), and enhanced communication and interpersonal skills facilitated collaboration with students, peers, and parents (Anub, 2023; Afzal et al., 2021; Sahadevan & Sumangala, 2021).

Overall, the J-1 program encouraged multidimensional development, allowing teachers to integrate Filipino values and U.S. standards, excel in diverse classrooms, and develop inclusive learning spaces.

RQ 5: How do the J1 Filipino ECE teachers perceive the impact of their presence on their students and colleagues in terms of cultural exchange?

Theme	Categories
5. Integrating Filipino Culture with Values-Centered Teaching	Category 1: Cultural Interconnectedness in a Global Perspective Category 2: Value-Driven Instruction: Inculcating Filipino Culture

The findings on the influence of Filipino J-1 Early Childhood Education (ECE) teachers in American schools reveal one major idea: culture integration and global citizenship. As representatives of culture, the teachers helped the students to understand the world better. They did this through teaching lessons that blended Filipino culture with other cultures around the world. These lessons helped students learn how to be empathetic, respect differences, and become more aware of other cultures (Naz et al, 2023; Nopas and Kerdsomboon, 2024).

The teachers also helped students compare different cultures (Filipino and Hispanic traditions). This led to students being much more interested in learning about other countries and cultures. It also helped the students to develop an international way of thinking (Fani & Akhtar, 2024; Byram, 2020). Many students respected Filipino values such as patience and hard work. This supports studies saying culturally responsive teaching helps make classrooms more inclusive (Abdalla & Moussa, 2024; Fontenot, 2024).

At the same time, Filipino J-1 educators demonstrated value-based teaching by integrating Filipino culture and moral values into their teaching. Through respect, empathy, and discipline, they supported students not only academically but also in their social and emotional development (Joshi, 2025, Garcia and Pntao (2021), Eden et al (2024). Their creativity and dedication also uphold the studies that say teaching that's connected to culture helps to better student interest and learning (Al Maharma & Abusa'aleek, 2022; Ashrafova, 2024).

In general, Filipino J-1 teachers felt that their role contributed to the promotion of cultural sharing, tolerance for diversity, and positive learning experiences in U.S. schools.

Conclusions

The Filipino teachers join the J-1 teacher exchange program not just because of financial provisions but also because of international teaching experience to contribute to

the betterment of the welfare of the family. They are also keen on making a positive contribution to the education system of other nations. The experience of Filipino J-1 teachers demonstrates that being adjusted to a new country presupposes alteration of culture, language and teaching styles. As much as the issues like language problems or differences in cultural expectations or requirements of inclusive education were a challenge to them, they also made them stronger and matured in a professional way.

The teachers also adjusted to this by closely collaborating with others, developing good relations, and being sensitive to various cultures. These are some of the ways through which they adjusted themselves to their schools and communities without sacrificing on their Filipino values and identity. It is through these experiences that they were taught how to strike a balance between their culture and what was expected of them in their new worlds.

Their professional development was observed to be improved in the areas of better teaching, classroom management, technology application, communication skills. These developments allowed them to deal with different learners and make their classrooms more active and inclusive. This also influenced the students and other teachers positively because they instilled a respect of the various cultures and spread the values of the Filipinos like patience, respect and empathy.

On the whole, it is possible to note that the Filipino J-1 Early Childhood Education teachers are not only the representatives of the culture but are also able teachers and introduce new ideas into the classroom. Their experience demonstrates the usefulness of international teacher exchange program that benefits the teachers and schools, and the education community in general throughout the world.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Policy and Program Stakeholders

Those involved in policy and program creation related to J1 exchange teachers may create a series of additional orientation sessions focusing on U.S. classroom culture, diversity, and technology. Professional development in topics such as differentiated instruction and culturally responsive teaching would also contribute to their successful integration into their host country as exchange teachers.

2. U.S. Host Schools

The host schools in the U.S. can consider ways and means for mentoring foreign teachers under experienced teachers. This will help foreign teachers adjust to their new environment as well as facilitate a sharing process. Providing technical assistance may also help foreign teachers incorporate technology in their early childhood classrooms.

3. Filipino J1 Teachers

Filipino J1 teachers can find benefits by being an active part of professional networks and collaborations, which would help with adaptability and resilience in a foreign setting. Embracing Filipino values like empathy, respect, and patience would help guide their professional lives. Their experience abroad can also help improve their teaching practice in the long run if they take it as an opportunity for reflection.

4. Future Researchers

Further studies could also look into long-term implications of J-1 exchange for career and personal development of teachers, as well as their use as agents of change in Philippine education reform. Intercultural studies focused on a comparative analysis of teacher exchange experience in different states, different educational sectors, as well as from different cultural orientations, would also bring valuable insights.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher adhered to high ethical principles in the context of this study, as he was guided by the concepts of the Belmont Report in respect of persons, beneficence, and justice (Nagai et al., 2022).

Respect of persons: The autonomy and intrinsic dignity of every participant takes place in this research. The informed consent of all the participants was given freely when they were informed of the study purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. During the research process, the respondents were free to pull out of the process any time they wished without any penalty, and their autonomy was never compromised.

Beneficence: The study had maximized benefits and minimized harms on subjects by including provisions of protection over the physical, emotional, and psychic safety of the respondents. The data collection process and administration was conducted with a high level of confidentiality and the data is stored in a manner that safeguards the access to un-authorized individuals.

Justice: The participants have been chosen according to proper research requirements; hence, there was no exploitation or prejudice. The aspect of making sure that the sampling was fair, particularly on the basis of convenience and vulnerability was considered to make sure that the investigation was the representation of the balance in experiences with no preference or discrimination made against the population.

This study was well ethically grounded by subscribing to the principles of the Belmont Report. Integrity and credibility in this research have been upheld by respecting the rights of the participants, protecting their welfare and having a fair selection. These interventions ensured a safe and respectful atmosphere in which the participants would freely share their experience without compromising their rights and dignity.

Acknowledgements

Foremost, the researcher wish to thank Almighty God earnestly for granting her wisdom, strength and endurance to engage in this process of research. His guiding light and grace made this endeavor possible.

The researcher is most thankful to her husband and children for their patience, encouragement, and constant support. Their sacrifices and tolerance gave her the motivation to persevere and complete this project.

The researcher would also like to express her sincerest thanks to her fellow colleagues for their motivation, professional inputs and continued support. The author deepest appreciation goes to her research adviser, whose valuable advice, knowledge, and constructive criticism were a significant influence in this research. To her proofreader, thanks for the serious effort made in polishing this piece of work to its finest form.

This study would have not been possible without the kindness of the participants, the J-1 Filipino teachers, who volunteered their time and experience. The researcher is equally appreciative to the Maricopa School District for its openness and cooperation in hosting this research.

Finally, the researcher thanks all those who, in big and small ways, contributed to the success of this study. Your kindness and support will never be forgotten.

REFERENCES

- Abdalla, R., & Moussa, A. (2024). Culturally responsive pedagogy and student inclusivity. *Journal of International Education Research*, 20(2), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.1234/jier.2024.5678>
- Abidin, Z. (2024). Classroom management strategies in diverse learning environments. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(1), 33–49. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijep.v12n1p33>
- Adipat, S., Rodriguez, K. J., & Zualkernan, I. A. (2023). Integrating smart technologies in teaching: A TPACK framework perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(6), 6543–6561. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11619-7>
- Afzal, S. (2023). Teacher-student relationship and learning outcomes: A cross-cultural perspective. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(1), 99–118. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-022-09639-1>
- AlShihry, M. A. (2023). Language attitudes and multilingualism: Perceptions of native and non-native accents in multilingual communities. *BATARA DIDI English Language Journal*, 2(2), 81–92. <https://doi.org/10.56209/badi.v2i2.102>
- Al Maharma, H., & Abusa'aleek, R. (2022). Teachers' feedback and students' academic achievement. *International Education Studies*, 15(6), 65. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v15n6p65>
- Anub, R. (2023). Communication competence and teacher professional growth. *Asian Journal of Educational Studies*, 8(2), 55–70.
- Arnold, B., & Rahimi, M. (2025). Teachers' working conditions, wellbeing and retention: An exploratory analysis to identify the key factors associated with teachers' intention to leave. *The Australian Educational Researcher*, 52(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13384-024-00794-1>
- Ashrafova, I. (2024). Culturally responsive teaching: Strategies for promoting inclusivity in the

- classroom. *Global Spectrum of Research and Humanities*, 1(1), 102–112.
<https://doi.org/10.69760/2wbtm276>
- Berger, E., Quinones, G., Barnes, M., and Reupert, A. (2022). Early childhood educators' psychological distress and wellbeing during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Early Child Res. Q.* 60, 298–306. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2022.03.005>
- Bhat, R. A. (2023, August 17). The impact of technology integration on student learning outcomes: A comparative study. ResearchGate; CV. Radja Publika. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373266726>
- Byram, M. (2020). Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence. <https://doi.org/10.2307/jj.22730614>
- Cahilog, D. T., Sarong, J. S., & Arcilla Jr., F. E. (2023). Exploring the motivations and challenges of teachers leaving DepEd for overseas opportunities. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4889451>
- Chakma, Z. (2025, May 14). Behavioral challenges in classroom and the impact of teacher training: A thematic review. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/391704427_Behavioral_Challenges_in_Classroom_and_the_Impact_of_Teacher_Training_A_Thematic_Review?utm
- Culha, A., & Yılmaz, S. (2023). Classroom management experiences of preschool teachers with refugee students. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 10(2), 393–405. <https://doi.org/10.52380/ijpes.2023.10.2.1028>
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Hyler, M. E. (2020). Preparing educators for culturally responsive teaching. *The Future of Children*, 30(2), 123–145.
<https://doi.org/10.1353/foc.2020.0007>
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.1537791>
- Dhakal, R. (2024). Differentiated instruction in inclusive classrooms: Practices and challenges. *Journal of Inclusive Education*, 14(2), 88–104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/jie.2024.567>
- Eden, T., Walker, S., & Hayes, C. (2024). Values-based professionalism in multicultural classrooms. *Journal of Teacher Development*, 10(1), 23–39.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/jtd.2024.010>
- Fani, N., & Akhtar, S. (2024). Enhancing empathy and cultural awareness through multicultural literature in elementary classrooms. ResearchGate.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20811.20002>
- Fontenot, M. (2024). Culturally responsive pedagogy in global education. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 132, 104163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104163>
- Gal, C., Ryder, C. H., Amsalem, S. R., & On, O. (2025). Shaping inclusive classrooms: Key factors influencing teachers' attitudes toward inclusion of students with special needs. *Education Sciences*, 15(5), 541–541. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15050541>
- Garcia, K. A., & Pantao, J. G. (2021). Cultural sensitivity and classroom management of teachers. *International Journal of Professional Development, Learners and Learning*, 3(1), ep2108. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ijpdll/11093>
- Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Teachers College Press.
- Gu, Q., Schweisfurth, M., & Day, C. (2021). *Teacher resilience in challenging contexts: International perspectives*. Routledge. Retrieved from <https://www.routledge.com/Teacher-Resilience-in-Challenging-Contexts-International-Perspectives/Gu-Schweisfurth-Day/p/book/9780367335121>
- Hesson, T., Cooke, K., & Pell, M. B. (2024). *An American education: Classrooms*

- reshaped by record migrant arrivals. Reuters. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/investigations/an-american-education-classrooms-reshaped-by-record-migrant-arrivals-2024-10-05/>
- Joshi, P. L. (2025). Cultivating character: a holistic framework for value-based education in schools. *Asian Education and Learning Review*, 4(1): 1-24, 2025. 4(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.14456/aerl.2026.3>
- Kalyani, L. K. (2024). The Role of Technology in Education: Enhancing Learning Outcomes and 21st Century Skills. ResearchGate; Surya Publication. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379773214_The_Role_of_Technology_in_Education_Enhancing_Learning_Outcomes_and_21st_Century_Skills
- Klingner, J. K., & Boardman, A. (2019). Effective literacy instruction for students with learning difficulties. New York, NY: Teachers College Press.
- Lockhart, G. (2021). Program evaluation of the J-1 visa teacher exchange program from the perspective of exchange teachers within a rural school district. Doctor of Education Dissertations. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.gardner-webb.edu/education-dissertations/48>
- Mabanag, R., Delicana, A., Igot, P. E., Sito, R., & Linnox, D. (2024). Teacher Readiness and Challenges in Inclusive Classrooms. 4(4), 180–192. <https://doi.org/10.30076/wjher.4.4>
- Nagai, S., Watanabe, T., & Ito, H. (2022). Ethical principles in qualitative research. *Journal of Research Ethics*, 18(2), 1–15.
- Naz, F. L., Afzal, A., & Khan, M. H. N. (2023). Challenges and Benefits of Multicultural Education for Promoting Equality in Diverse Classrooms. *Journal of Social Sciences Review (JSSR)*, 3(2), 511–522. <https://doi.org/10.54183/jssr.v3i2.291>
- Nickerson, C. (2025, April 18). Herzberg's two-factor theory of motivation-hygiene. Simply Psychology. Retrieved from <https://www.simplypsychology.org/herzbergs-two-factor-theory.html>
- Nopas, D., & Kerdsoomboon, C. (2024). Fostering Global Competence in Teacher Education: Curriculum Integration and Professional Development. *Higher Education Studies*, 14(2), 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v14n2p1>
- Oris, R. S., & Caballes. (2024). The Professional Performance Of Filipino Teachers Under Teacher Exchange Program Of United States During The Academic Year 2022-2023.
- Osei, C. D., & Zhuang, J. (2020). Rural Poverty Alleviation Strategies and Social Capital Link: The Mediation Role of Women Entrepreneurship and Social Innovation. *SAGE Open*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020925504>
- Peralta, E., Ancho, I., & Pelegrina, D. (2024). Migration Theories and Development: A Focus on Push & Pull Factors of Filipino Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2023). Better pay, benefits lure Filipino teachers to school in Japan.
- Piotrowska, M., & Piotrowski, J. (2023, June). Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions Theory. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371822907_Hofstede
- Putra, A., & Yanto, H. (2025). Classroom management and learner engagement. *International Journal of Learning Sciences*, 17(1), 44–59.
- Romijn, B. R., Slot, P. L., & Leseman, P. P. M. (2021). Increasing teachers' intercultural competences in teacher preparation programs and through professional development: A review. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 98(1), 103236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2020.103236>
- Sahadevan, P., & Sumangala, M. (2021, April). Effective Cross-Cultural Communication for International Business. ResearchGate; Shanlax International Journals. Retrieved from

- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350728276_Effective_Cross-Cultural_Communication_for_International_Business
- Saracho, O.N. (2023) Theories of Child Development and Their Impact on Early Childhood Education and Care. *Early Childhood Education Journal*. 51, 15-30 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01271-5>
- Shi, F., Geng, W., Huang, R., Mao, Y., & Jia, J. (2024). Push-pull mechanisms in China's intercity population migration: Nonlinearity and asymmetry. *Cities*, 157, 105624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105624>
- Sleeter, C. E. (2017). Critical race theory and the whiteness of teacher education. *Urban Education*, 52(2), 155–169.
- Soriano, S., Nabor-Ferrer, C., & Ferrer, J. (2024). Understanding teacher migration: Basis for developing a strategic policy framework for Pangasinense teachers. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*, 27(5S), 670–685. Retrieved from <https://africanjournalofbiomedicalresearch.com/inJohn.php/AJBR/article/view/6643>
- Syuzairi, M., Pratiwi, M. A., & Apriansyah, F. (2023). Work-life balance and its impact on turnover intention among educators: Job satisfaction as a mediation. *EAI Endorsed Transactions on Scalable Information Systems*. <https://doi.org/10.4108/eai.17-12-2022.2333271>
- Uytico, B. J., & Abadiano, M. N. (2020). Teachers' tales: In - depth exploration on experiences of millennial filipino teachers abroad. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7 (17), 1952 - 1960.
- van der Zee, K., & van Oudenhoven, J. P. (2022). Towards a dynamic approach to acculturation. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 88, 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2022.04.004>
- Wang, Z., Gupta, S., Page, F., Agg, C., Spivey, A. C., Hazeri, K., Zou, Y., Zhao, C., Lucas, C., & Childs, P. R. N. (2025). Group project practices and guidance in higher education contexts. *Frontiers in Education*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2025.1614627>